

Figure S1: IQ-tree of ChC-candidate genes (Supplementary 1: Table S3) and the *L. niger* candidates obtained by blast to infer orthology. All protein IDs starting with "KMQ" are *L. niger* proteins. The ones highlighted in red were differentially expressed between acclimation treatments.

Figure S2: Zsummary preservation scores for a) single species and b) species pairs, based on results from module preservation analyses.

Fig. S3 Number of read-counts for the DEGs detected in each species.

As indicated by pairwise Mann-Whitney U tests, read numbers only differ weakly between *L. brunneus* and *L. niger* ($p=0.014$), but not between *L. brunneus* and *L. platythorax* ($p=0.728$), which would have been expected if read numbers were influenced by backmapping rates in our data.